

Collaborative Reflexive/Reflective Teaching and Action Research in TESL

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Abstract—Teaching English as a Second Language (TESL) has become a very rich area of research. Practitioners or teachers of English as a foreign or a second language are now promoting both collaborative learning and collaborative teaching. Students learning a language collaboratively and cooperatively are learning in a better environment of team work where they learn from each other. Further, teaching English collaboratively also creates an enriching environment that is also very enriching to students' and teachers' experiences of learning and teaching. Moreover, action research stems from actual teacher concerns and students' needs. Reflection in turn, on the experience of the material taught and the delivery of material is becoming an integral part of the teaching and learning experience self- evaluation and self-development. In this case, the concern of the research field in the area of TESL will be the development of teaching delivery, material and quality of learning. In the present research, the TESL module taught to year two students in the Faculty of Arts and Humanities, British University in Egypt (BUE) will be evaluated reflexively by the students and teachers. The module was taught to students in two different specialisms. It was taught and delivered through collaborative teaching and was evaluated by both teachers and students as very successful and enjoyable. The reflections of both teachers and students as well as student results confirm that it was a success.

Keywords—Action research, addressing differentiation, collaborative teaching, reflective teaching and learning, reflexive learning, reflexive teaching, self-development, self-evaluation, TESL.

I. LITERATURE AND THEORY REVIEW

TEACHERS of English as a second language in several areas are now encouraged and are encouraging others to become actively involved in action research where they reflect and collaborate during all of the stages of teaching: module planning, material preparation, delivering the modules collaboratively, even in assessment and evaluation. Action research, collaborative teaching, reflective reflexive teaching and co teaching are all inter-related. These topics will all be reviewed here-under. The present research paper will attempt to show how they were applied in the case of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities (FOA), BUE and more specifically to the Department of English Language and Literature (DELL). It will also present a suggestion of a structured model within the existing system at BUE that can be later used by the instructors who are expected to collaborate whether as co-teachers or as senior- junior staff collaboratively in a reflexive action research environment.

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A. Collaborative Learning to Collaborative Teaching

In the area of teaching and learning, the shift towards technologically supported collaborative learning [1] is becoming of age. A good review of education technology collaborative learning is found in [2]. Collaboration in the teaching environment should promote discussion and dialogue through reflection on problem solving and feedback. Collaboration in face to face and through technological tools is believed to be a means to educational achievement [3]. Interpersonal competence through collaborative practices was confirmed by several research and surveys, e.g. [4]. Furthermore, students' and teachers' perspectives of obstacles or pitfalls of effective learner collaboration were investigated by many researchers, e.g. [5]. Student-staff partnership in student teachers' training is a sort of collaboration that was also recently studied in research showing how this relationship is related to the concept of action research (AR) in research-based education [6]. Investigating student teachers, prospective teachers or in-service student teachers were also investigated [7]-[9].

B. Collaborative AR in EFL

Promoting research lead instruction is emphasized in the area of teaching. The main target is the students' effective learning, empowering them in classroom practices [10] and teachers' achievement of the learning objectives [11]. Through AR, teachers of English need to and want to reflect on developing and improving collaboratively their teaching of English [12], [13].

Burns [12] and recently [14] reviewed and updated the work done in English language teaching (ELT) on AR and how it has become an essential perspective and teacher practice in the past two decades. Teachers of English should have a system that supports them and allows them to develop their professional practice. It explains the impact that this practice would have on the discipline of ELT. While teachers can study together and can understand theories before and after applying theories to their teaching, they also reflected, took action and planned their work collaboratively. On the other hand, they faced the challenges of taking up an extra load as well as other challenges that are related to interpersonal issues and logistics that it involves. Nevertheless, AR prepares the informed empowered teacher researcher to be able to self-evaluate and self-develop. ELT bodies and organizations like the British Council [15], [16] and others [17] have sponsored and supported projects and/or research at universities, encouraging the promotion of the ELT action researcher.

The research of [17] explains the possible ways of meeting the challenges that AR in ELT presents, while [15] and [16] researched the student teacher researcher and confirm how reflection and collaboration are now a necessity for teaching and learning development. A teacher researcher is a teacher with a reflexive reflective mentality that would fit in a system that would continuously develop and continuously improve and keep up with the era.

AR is the teacher's systematic reflection, dialogic questioning, collaborative planning, and reflexive decision making of change and development [18]. It is directly linked to teachers' professional development, whether at the elementary or primary school level [19]-[21], the university level [22], or for pre-service student teachers [23]. It also targets the students' best interest [10], [11]. Furthermore, it involves administrators as well. Without organizational support AR would be difficult or rather impossible to implement. It should be part of the organizational development plan system and instructors should get support and guidance with using the tools. A good example is project and/or material development support, e.g. [24], [25].

Techniques, material and systems for carrying out AR are created, put together and prepared for pre-service, in-service, and student teacher support and use [8], [23], [26].

C. Collaborative Reflexive and Reflective Teaching

AR by nature involves reflexive and reflective teaching. As teacher researchers collaborate or co-teacher, they need to employ reflexive reflective practices.

The arguments about the difference between reflective and reflexive teaching [9], [27], [28] in the literature are resolved in the present paper by describing 'reflection' as a state of self-observation 1) reflection in-action: while teaching, 2) reflection on action: after teaching [29]. In [30], the term 'reflection for action' would add to the value or purpose of reflection in teacher education. Furthermore, [30] explains how prospective teachers should be ready to self-observe, self-analyze and self-evaluate even before taking up the teaching career. Pre-service, new teachers, and in-service teachers must

take up 'reflexive practice' for their professional development. In this context, 'reflexive' was used synonymously with 'reflective'. Reflective practice was defined and promoted by numerous researchers. It was promoted by organizations for their staff professional development [31], [32]; more so, for the teachers of English as a foreign/second language [33].

Reflexive practice, as opposed to reflective, is the deep internal introspective monitoring of detailed actions (verbal, nonverbal, feelings, thoughts, responses and problem solving) of every step of the act of teaching *after* the teaching takes place. Reflexive practice entails making decisions and taking action for the development by changing a strategy, procedure, method, tool or material. It involves re-planning, restructuring and reorganizing. Self-criticism, self-evaluation and self-development of one's teaching in action, on action, and for action is reflective practice [30]. While the reflexive practice is retrospective and introspective [9], it involves making decisions and taking the action of change for development [34] that was drawn from reflective practice [30], [35], [36].

Since the target of reflective and reflexive practice is both professional development and achieving learning outcomes, the cyclic nature of reflective practice needs to be ongoing so that the development of both instructors and instruction would be in turn continuous and ongoing as well. As in Fig. 1 [27], for example, the simplification of the cyclic process involved in reflective reflexive practice is continuous.

Teachers and administration should be keen on supporting research and further, the results of research should be disseminated and made use of in the practice. The principle of reflexive practice (PRP) as defined in [27], encourages, examines and follows up on whether research results were beneficial by reflexively studying and criticizing research: designs, methods, tools and results, and developing the techniques by making the decisions of their change and development. PRP is a prescriptive. By reflexively studying research results they suggest advice and solutions confirmed by research; therefore, applying the results or improving on research techniques.

Fig. 1 Being reflexive about designing contexts for learning design [27]

Student teachers or teachers in service by default should be reflective reflexive researchers collaboratively. The dialogic

planning, reflecting, making decisions for change, uses evidence based reflection [15] and supporting development.

The teacher researcher must relate reflective reflexive practice to learning objectives and tasks must be linked to assessment designs [15] to improve the reflective practice.

In two recent studies, student teachers' perceptions and views of reflective practice were examined. The first [37] confirmed that teaching staff members believed that reflective practice was very essential, important and useful. In the second [23], it was explained how teachers of English as a second language in their reflexive practice were using reflective journals and interviews, and that the practice enabled them to relate theories they learned in their modules to their practicum. They found the experience very useful and enlightening; it practicalized their knowledge.

D. Collaborative Teaching and Co-Teaching in EFL

Studies done on teacher collaboration were reviewed in [38] where the terminology used in the area of collaboration was identified. Some of these include: 'teacher collaboration', 'lecturer team', 'professor collaboration' and 'cooperation teachers', which are close to the type of collaboration the present research will use. Also discussed is the concept of collaboration and its positive facilitating nature. Moreover, challenges or hindrances of collaboration described are issues to be addressed through decisions and support for collaboration. In spite of all challenges, effective collaboration must be the organizational target since it is believed to be the best role model for students who will in turn collaborate in society.

Collaborative teaching involves continuous evaluation, dialogue, collaborative reflection, decision making, action taking and reevaluation. A review of teacher collaboration in [39] confirmed the importance of teacher collaboration. The study surveyed teachers in five districts in the US of elementary, middle, and high special needs schools, including English language teachers, as well as administrators. The research confirmed that collaboration and teaming up of instructors is essential for instructional innovation, school improvement or development, and achieving students learning outcomes. It is believed, and confirmed by this survey that administrative support is most essential to have a structured system of reflexive collaborative teaching in an institution.

Many other research studied school teachers' experiences of collaborating teams in mathematics, science, physical education and social studies, for example in [40], which also confirmed the challenges of lack of collaboration regularly scheduled time, among other challenges that need administrative support. Another example is that of collaboration between teachers of urban elementary schools of students with disabilities, as in [41]. These teachers already have their own special challenges that can be resolved by collaboration with specialized practitioners. Teachers, researchers and administrators in schools believe that collaboration is the best solution. Therefore, they all must support higher-quality collaboration in order to serve the teachers' benefits of professional development and students' good learning culture at university [42]. On the other hand, the area of EFL/ESL collaboration was also seen as one of the

good strategies of teaching for solving problems [43]. Dialogue, developing strategies, coping with existing or future classroom problems, and decisions of changing of their classroom practices were part of the process of development with the support and guidance of supervisors, researchers, or possibly co-teachers. Collaborative reflection is also viewed as solving many problems in EFL/ESL at the university level in teacher education [44]. Teachers would share knowledge in dialogue and journal writing. They would reflect with their peers, mentors, supervisors or researcher to be able to deal with problems. They deconstruct, develop, transform and change. In [45], examples of questions that were used for reflective questioning during collaborative dialogue were exemplified to be employed and explored by researchers and survey constructors. They support thinking aloud and could be further expanded to extend follow up questions. It is believed that the practice of collaborative reflective reflexive practice in AR will enable cognitive transformation in ELT [46]. Systemizing and structuring the process is therefore essential for university EFL/ESL, giving instructors time to have systematic dialogue, assistance by feedback, administrative support by allowing the system to give them space to reflect and change through effective collaboration. Furthermore, and more importantly, EFL/ESL instructors need to be able to be prepared to co-plan before they co-teach [47].

E. Co-Teaching and Senior-Junior Model

In co-teaching, co-planning is one the most important preparatory integral stages of working together. The co-teaching partnership entails parity [48]. In preparation for collaborative co-teaching, clarifying the responsibilities and defining division as well as integration of labor, needs to be clearly systematized in co-teaching [49]. The concept of equity/equitability in co-teaching is essential [50]. At the same time, co-teachers must complement each other (i.e. contribute extra features in such a way as to improve or emphasize each other's quality). Co-teaching has several types of collaboration models in the literature: 1) the general educator-special educator model, i.e. in inclusion classrooms, e.g. [48]-[52]; 2) native-nonnative speaker model, e.g. [53], [54], among others. In the present research, two models, particular of the DELL, BUE setting, in the same discipline of teaching English Literature, Applied Linguistics or Translation, will be suggested, namely *Model A*: two senior co-teachers with the same academic status: 'Senior- Senior' or 'Senior- New Senior' and *Model B*: senior staff-teaching assistant (TA): 'Senior-Junior'/'Lecturer-TA'. Therefore, the co-teaching reflective reflexive AR model here will refer to either model A or model B. In the literature, co-teaching within a systematic structure is believed to be a gap that needs to be filled [55].

II. HIGHER EDUCATION SETTING: DELL, FOA, BUE

In higher education, the Egyptian private university setting collaboration is an acceptable concept but is not systematized nor structured in the system. It is also not under the umbrella of AR nor is it using reflective reflexive practice as a technique for development. It is rather an ad hoc development

of the syllabus, ad hoc curriculum change, and very limited number of workshops offered for staff development. At the BUE setting, the University Teaching and Learning Committee (UTLC) and the University staff development coordination there is built-in structured system of development is in place. All faculties must follow yearly the development cycle. First, on the administrative level, the university supports development through the university's Annual Quality Enhancement and Committee Cycle. All suggested, discussed and approved changes are feasibly ready for implementation as per an Annual Program Review (APR). The quality cycle system schedules a monthly Faculty Teaching and Learning Committee (FTLC) followed by a monthly UTLC. These are then followed by an Annual Cycle Action Plan (AP) that had been discussed and approved before changes take place in programs or program modules. Second, on the level of academic staff development, the Staff Development Committees are scheduled in all of the university faculties, on the university level. The schedule is also disseminated to faculties, each scheduling and administering workshops and induction sessions to enhance the execution, application and monitoring of staff induction and development. Further, for new staff induction and development there is also a system in place for peer observation and feedback meetings. Dialogue and collaboration is therefore possible. The individual staff development workshop needs and requests would be collected and compiled by the administrative staff. All the requested supporting workshops would then be sent to university staff development coordinator. These requested workshops would be considered, prepared and scheduled in the next academic staff development plan. Thus, the university is addressing all or most of the individual needs of staff for their professional development. Thirdly, on the student bodies' level, Student Staff Liaison Committees (SSLC) are held biannually to get feedback from students on staff performance, program gaps and student needs. It is believed that the students are important partners of the teaching and learning process [56].

The FOA's vision is to provide quality education and conducting research that contributes to the development of Egypt, and hopefully the Middle East region [57].

It is believed therefore that including a set system to adopt a reflective reflexive collaborative teaching practice through implementing departmental AR would be possible since it is a necessity for quality education. This will be a suggested model for implementation in FOA, DELL, at BUE but can be adapted elsewhere. The model will be referred to as collaborative reflective reflexive action research (CRRAR).

III. MODELS AND SUGGESTED STRUCTURE: MATERIAL, TECHNIQUES, METHODS AND PROCEDURES PROPOSED TO BE EMPLOYED

A. Model A of Co-Teaching and Model B of Collaboration

Model A is where two senior co-teachers with same academic status are co-teaching. These have two sub-types: 'Senior-Senior' or 'Senior-New Senior.' This first existing model of collaboration is already part of the system in the

FOA, DELL. Teachers either self-select their pair or are assigned the module together as per the specialism and the departmental needs. The Senior-Senior co-teaching model consists of two senior staff: PhD holders, an associate professors or professors, and is common. This model is usually a balanced one where both staff members are aware of the importance of collaboration even though they might not have systematically collaborated nor co-taught in a module before.

The next step is co-planning. After assignment, both parties are sent module specifications and start meeting up for brainstorming and planning for writing up and preparing course work briefs which include a weekly plan and all course work assessments. The planning meetings also include deciding on textbooks or reading lists for class use, eLearning material and students' independent study materials. Basic items that would be included in final assessments would be agreed upon during these initial planning meetings. In later stages when final assessments are being prepared, final decisions of actual question items would be finalized collaboratively as well. Co lesson planning on a daily or at least a weekly basis must be part of the structure. Instructors need to schedule mutual planning time preparing for their co-instruction.

Division of labor is usually done as per the stronger abilities of specialisms in each participant. They either alternate their teaching, station teach, team teach, or parallel teach teaching or one leads and the other supports, see the example in Fig. 2 [58].

Fig. 2 Five Co-Teaching Models [58]

If the collaboration is between a staff member who is more senior with another staff that is less senior, the relation and coordination is sort of closer to Model B, since the more senior staff member would have more experience and knowledge which would be useful and mentoring for the new PhD-earned staff. Meanwhile, incoming staff might have more input regarding updated new technology teaching media.

Model B is where senior staff, PhD holders, Associate Professors, or Professors, collaboratively teach with a teaching assistant (TA): 'Senior-Junior/TA'. In this model, the senior staff is the moderator, as well as the main contributor, is mentoring and supporting the junior staff member and is collaborating in training staff to reflect and learn how to collaboratively make decisions, implement change, re-evaluate and re-plan to develop modules, tasks, materials, and

assessments. Junior staff also contribute innovative technology enhanced student-centered material and techniques; they are closer to the students' age and are more aware of students' interests. They are able to select motivating topics.

In both models, collaboration, cooperation, reflection, action decision making, and implementation of change is taking place in the reflective meetings of both members actively contributing to all the steps.

In collaborative AR, activity staff members, senior and junior, meet regularly and frequently to set new goals for development and change, plan, and engage in decisions for interventions, data collection, data analysis and report writing. The involvement can range from full involvement to support of finding resources, helping to collect data and suggesting analyzing strategies.

Having the setup where there is already a system in the university that allows staff development and staff collaboration by being aware of the need through reflection, is an asset. The experience of co teaching excludes two of the most critical obstacles hindering reflective teaching and in turn collaborative teaching. These two obstacles are: 1) allowing time for reflection meetings in staff schedules and 2) supporting development and syllabus change in the syllabus as a result of reflexive teaching [59], [60].

Having surveyed whether instructors and staff members are aware of the system and whether they practice collaboration, a survey was done and the results are as follows:

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE SURVEY RESULTS

Question number	Question content	Percentage of information/agreement
1	Teaching years of experience	78.95% were more than 10 years of experience
2	Teaching Department	89.47% were teachers of DELL
3	Collaborative curriculum planning teachers worked together	52.63% 'Very Often' 31.58% 'Often', 10.53% 'Occasionally', and 5.26% 'Never'
4	Collaborative worked together extra curriculum activity	26.32% 'Very Often' 42.11% 'Often', 31.58% 'Occasionally', and 0% 'Never'
5	Have a mentor for collaborative teaching	'Yes' 55.58% and 'No' 44.44%
6	The department provides support for collaborative teaching	'Yes' 100%
7	Most important aspect of collaborative teaching	63.16% 'Enriched Atmosphere' 'Curriculum Support' 31.58% 'Moral Support' 5.26% and 'Advice' 0%
8	Collaborative teaching increases student learning	84.21% 'Strongly Agree' 15.79% 'Agree'
9	Practicing collaborative teaching increased 'my' instructional practice	42.11% 'Strongly Agree' 57.89% 'Agree'
10	In collaborative teaching, students at risk are discussed and their problems are addressed	42.11% 'Strongly Agree' 42.11% 'Agree', and 15 % 'Neutral'

C. CRRAR Co-Planning Techniques and Scheduling

Four main stages of co-planning would be: first, before module delivery (in preparation for course work briefs): 2-3 meetings before the start of teaching; second, during module delivery: weekly reflective reflexive meetings (in process of lesson planning); third, mid-semester final exam planning (planning and setting the final assessment); finally, before final exam revision and agreeing marking criteria application. Parallel to the assessments (formative and summative), marking and double marking meetings are held after administering any course work formative assessments as well as after final exam administration. These are all followed by reflexive meetings for future co-planning for development of a

B. BUE, FOA, Survey Results on Collaborative Teaching

A survey was shared and was responded to by staff, Table I is a summary of the responses and the percentages in the statistics.

An analysis of the results show that staff in the FOA, BUE is all (100%) aware of collaborative teaching: question '6', asking about the support the departments give for 'collaborative teaching.' They all also agree collaborative teaching practice supported their 'instructional practice,' 42.11% 'Strongly Agree' 57.89% 'Agree'. Moreover, there was an agreement that staff planned collaboratively 52.63% 'Very Often' and 42.11% 'Often.' They also thought that even in extra curriculum activities they collaborated and worked together. While, 55.58% agreed that they received mentoring in collaborative teaching and 44.44% did not. Therefore, the area that needs further support is mentoring staff in the practice of collaboration. Collaborative teaching is unanimously believed to support and increase the student's learning: 84.21% 'Strongly Agree' and 15.79% 'Agree.'

An important support on the part of the BUE, FOA development plan is the system that allows collaboration and development of the program, staff, and students. It is suggested in the present research that there should be a structured plan, schedule and follow up forms for mentoring and ensuring its delivery and application.

module assessment strategy. The action to be taken is decided in these meetings: either to keep the strategy, change or slightly improve it. In co-teaching, in its different models (Model A or B) or types [58]: supportive, parallel, complementary, and team co-teaching, co-teachers will schedule reflexive meetings for co-planning [61]. Co-planning in co-teaching is one of the most important dialogic reflexive decision-making developmental techniques. It is believed to be a practical solution for teachers and learners [48].

Lesson planning in particular is another micro planning procedure that needs to be reflexively and collaboratively co planned. An easy collaborative media could be the use of a 'wiki' [62]. It is a means by which teachers can collaborate

and reflect in viral meetings at each participant's convenient time. It is believed to have a positive impact on teachers' classroom performance.

D. Methods for Follow up: Forms, Checklists and Proforma for Collaborative Reflexive Meetings

How are EFL teachers guided as to how they would practice reflection? What techniques do they need to use in the process? These are questions that can be answered. Many websites, teacher blogs and research provided techniques and working sheets/proforma to be employed in the process. In [63], the simple question, 'why do I need to reflect?' is raised and suggested techniques and procedures are suggested. The simplest of which is teachers' *diary keeping* and *peer observation*. The first stage of collaborative reflection is individual teacher *self-reflection* and *journal writing*. Teachers must be self-critical. Reference [64] suggested that self-videoing and self-evaluation is an initiator of reflective teaching. Self-reflection is a necessary step towards collaborative reflexive teaching.

Self-observation and peer observation (PO) are both important procedures that are part of reflexive teaching. PO of new staff is part of the BUE professional development plan (PDP). Staff is observed by senior more experienced staff. Three parts of the process are in place. An initial meeting is held to orient the new staff member with the procedure, and to agree the observation session time and place. They also agree on where the observer will sit in class and how he/she will be introduced to the students. Part one of the 'Peer Observation' form is completed by the observee. It will include information related to the observee, the class session objective and the material the teacher will use. Hard copies will be provided. Part two is filled by the observer, including the positive and negative aspects observed in the classroom session and related to staff class session management. These reflections are then discussed in the second meeting and agreed. The third part is the space where the observer can add comments, objections and their personal staff development needs. These are then taken into consideration in the FOA staff development plan (SDP). Scheduling of workshops that address these needs is annually done. Moreover, this cycle of PO should be extended half annually to the continuing staff as part of SDP as well as part of the collaborative reflexive teaching.

The simple cycle of reflection [65] should become the default system to enhance teaching and learning. It is believed the more reflexive the teaching, the more effective it is for the student learning. In each step we need to stop and reflect, practice then collaborate continuously in every step of the way. Many blogs and teacher websites encourage and support reflexive teaching, guiding teachers through the process [66]-[69].

Through technologically enhanced material and techniques teachers can collaborate and reflect more effectively. Not only websites, blogs and hubs, but also through collaborative search engines teachers can collaborate for their reflexive teaching [70]. Web searches were investigated and new and more advanced engines were created for the collaborative

teaching purposes. Furthermore, both Wikis and Wikipedia were used as teaching tools [71]. Wiki-based activities and wiki spaces were employed in reflexive peer collaboration for second language writing skills teaching and development of [72]. Technology enhanced teaching saves effort, time and energy. It is recommended here as a means of effective collaboration and reflexive teaching techniques.

E. CRRAR Procedures: Value and Benefits Structured Reflexive Meetings

Several guides that have explicit guidelines for collaborative reflexive teaching in AR were designed, described and provided. As early as [73], self-reporting, lesson recording, PO, journal writing and diary keeping were part of reflective practice procedures for teacher education. In [74], for teachers in training and for teacher educators in ESL, a more detailed sampling of material, procedures, questionnaires, surveys and reflection questions are provided. The useful samples of guidelines for PO, collaborative reflexive journal keeping and AR step-by-step procedures are very useful and adaptable to all EFL/ESL teaching situations. Many studies in the field of EFL/ESL showed that reflective teaching had a very strong impact on staff development and on the students' learning, e.g. [75], [13], [16]. Furthermore, researchers and teachers in the field of EFL/ESL valued strongly CRRAR. Graduate online and on site courses for teacher students and/or educators are made available, guiding teachers on reflective collaborative teaching practices [76]. These explain the benefits and values of the new direction of teaching in the classroom. Blogs [77], [78] also interactively called for communities of teachers practicing reflexive collaborative teaching also showing, from experience, its benefits and values. Therefore, the call for structured CRRAR is deemed absolutely necessary [79].

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR A STRUCTURED CRRAR

In the present BUE, FOA, DELL setting, the structured system allows development and has space for both reflexive teaching and development. Therefore, the recommendation is to extend it into a structured schedule and a teacher's guide manual adapting all the suggested techniques, procedures, and forms to be available for instructors as a way of support that would be kept for future teachers to use collaboratively and faculty-wide.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is recommended that the structured systematized CRRAR cycle would be in place for adoption by the university higher education setting. Both the co-teaching model A, as well as the senior-Junior academic staff model B, could use the manual in future reflexive collaborative teaching practice. The BUE already has the privilege of its system of SDP, PDR, AP, PO. Since DELL staff is already practicing reflexive teaching and are creating the teachers' manual for their CRRAR experience, other faculties can also use the manual. CRRAR model suggested here can be the solution for some teaching and learning problems if implemented.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Burns, "Why you should create a collaborative classroom this year," in *Getting Smart*, 2018. <https://www.gettingsmart.com/2018/10/why-you-should-create-a-collaborative-classroom-this-year/s>
- [2] H. Keser and F. Özdamli, "What are the trends in collaborative learning studies in 21st century?" in *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 46, Elsevier, Science Direct online, 2012, pp. 157-161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.086>
- [3] R. Chandra, "Collaborative learning for educational achievement," in *IOSR International Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2015, uploaded by R. Chandra on 23 September 2017, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313889863>
- [4] E. H. Barros, "Collaborative learning in the translation classroom: preliminary survey results," in *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, no.16, 2011, pp. 42-60.
- [5] H. Le, J. Janssen and T. Wubbels, "Collaborative learning practices: teacher and student perceived obstacles to effective student collaboration," in *Cambridge Journal of Education*, vol. 48, no. 1, 2018 Published online: 13 Jan 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2016.1259389>
- [6] J. Marie, "The relationship between research-based education and student-staff partnerships: Ways to connect research and teaching," in *Shaping higher education with students*, UCL Press and JSTOR, Ch 1.2, 2018, pp. 30- 40. DOI: 10.2307/j.ctt21c4tm.8, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt21c4tm.8>
- [7] Y. Reed, H. Davis and T. Nyabanyaba, "Investigating teachers' 'take-up' of reflective practice from an in-service professional development teacher education programme in South Africa," in *Educational Action Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2002, pp. 253-274, Routledge, 2011, (Online) Journal homepage: <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/rea20>
- [8] O. Sert, "Classroom interaction and language teacher education," in S. Walsh and S. Mann (Eds) *The Routledge Handbook of English Language Teacher Education*, Ch 15, London: Routledge, 2019, pp. 216-238. <https://www.routledge.com/The-Routledge-Handbook-of-English-Language-Teacher-Education-1st-Edition/Walsh-Mann/p/book/9781138961371> action research reflective teaching and collaboration reviews
- [9] T. Ryan, "When you reflect are you also being reflexive?" in *Ontario Action Researcher*, vol. 8, no. 1, article 2, 2005. ERIC online: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ844460>
- [10] J. J. C. León and C. M. C. Clastro, "Transforming EFL classroom practices and promoting students' empowerment: Collaborative learning from a dialogical approach," in *PROFILE*, vol. 19, no. 2, July-December 2017, (online), Bogotá, Colombia, pp. 135-149, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318213825>
- [11] H. Harris and T. Bretag, "Reflective and collaborative teaching practice: Working towards quality student learning outcomes," in *Quality in Higher Education*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2003, pp. 179-185. DOI: 10.1080/13538320308151
- [12] A. Burns, *Collaborative action research for English language teachers*, Cambridge Language Teaching Library, Cambridge University Press, 1999. Transferred to digital printing 2005, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/245686550_Collaborative_action_research_for_English_teachers
- [13] A. Cirocki and R. Farrelly, "Research and reflective practice in the EFL classroom: Voices from Armenia," in *Eurasian Journal of Applied Linguistics (EJAL)*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2016, pp. 31-56. www.ejal.eu
- [14] A. Burns, "Action research in English language teaching: Contributions and recent developments," in X. Gao, Ed., *Second Handbook of English Language Teaching*, Springer International Handbooks of Education, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2019, pp 1-15.
- [15] S. Walsh, "SETTVEO: Evidence-based reflection and teacher development," in *Teaching English ELT Research Papers 19.05*, London: British Council 2019, pp. 1-24. www.britishcouncil.org
- [16] D. Hunter and G. Gibson, "Embracing assessment: Improving reflective practice by task and assessment design," in *Teaching English ELT Research Papers 19.04*, London: British Council 2019. www.britishcouncil.org form for reflection and an assessment rubric assessment criteria.
- [17] P. Pardede, "Action research in EFL Learning and Teaching," in *Proceeding of EED Collegiate Forum 2015-2018. "EFL Theory and Practice: Voice of EED UKI"*, P. Pardede, Ed, Jakarta: UKI, 2019, pp. 136-146.
- [18] G. S. C. Hine, "The importance of action research in teacher education programs," in *Issues in Educational Research*, vol. 23, no. 2, 2013, pp. 151-163. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier23/hine.html>
- [19] S. Korucukis, "Professional journey through action research: A case of primary school teachers in an EFL context," in *The International Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2014, pp. 30-46.
- [20] K. Lyngsnes, "A reflexive eye on a collaborative action research project in school," in *The Qualitative Report*, vol. 21, no. 2, 2016, pp. 196-211. Retrieved from <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol21/iss2/3>
- [21] F. Dehghan and R. Sahragard, "Iranian EFL teachers' views in action research and its application in their classroom: a case study," in *Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 4, no.1, 2015, pp. 39-52.
- [22] T. Huang, "An action research on fostering critical thinking in EFL writing through formative assessment and feedback," in *Contemporary Educational Research Quarterly*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2016, pp. 81-105. DOI: 10.6151/CERQ.2016.2401.03
- [23] J. Yin, "Connecting theory and practice in teacher education: English-as-a-foreign-language pre-service teachers' perceptions of practicum experience," *Innovation and Education*, vol 1, no. 4, 2019.
- [24] British Council, "Action research toolkit," Kathmandu: British Council, 2015.
- [25] "Reflective practice guide," in: College of Policing 2017. https://www.cipd.co.uk/Images/reflective-practice-guide_tcm18-12524.pdf
- [26] S. Z. Ahmad, "Pedagogical action research projects to improve the teaching skills of Egyptian EFL student teachers," in *Proceedings of ICERI2012 Conference 19th-21st November 2012*, Madrid: Spain, pp 3589-3598.
- [27] Y. Reich, "The principle of reflexive practice," in *Design Research*, vol. 3, no. e4, Cambridge University Press, 2017, pp. 1-27, journals.cambridge.org/dsj DOI: 10.1017/dsj.2017.3 participatory action research(PAR)
- [28] D. Chinn, "Reflection and reflexivity," in *Clinical Psychology Forum 178, British Psychological Society*, October 2007.Uploaded by Deborah Chinn on 14 May 2019, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292453531>
- [29] V. Griffiths, "The reflective dimension in teacher education," in *International Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 33, Elsevier Science Ltd., 2000, pp. 539-555. Uploaded by Vivienne Griffiths on 27 January 2018, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222953641>.
- [30] M. M. Stingu, "Reflexive practice in teacher education: facts and trends," in *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 33, Elsevier, 2012, pp. 617 – 621. www.sciencedirect.com
- [31] "Resources for reflective practice" in: College of Policing 2017. file:///C:/Users/Owner/Downloads/Resources_for_reflective_practice_v1_0.pdf, in: https://www.college.police.uk/What-we-do/Development/professional-development-programme/Pages/CPD_how_-_a_toolkit.aspx,
- [32] P. Mathew, P. Mathew, and P. J. Peechattu, "Reflective practices: A means to teacher development," in *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology (APJCECT)*, vol 3, no 1, 2017, pp126-131 www.apiar.org.au
- [33] M. L. O. Mesa, "Reflective teaching: An approach to enrich the English teaching professional practice," in *HOW* vol. 25, no. 2, Bogotá: Colombia: July/December 2018, pp. 149-170. <https://doi.org/10.19183/how.25.2.386>
- [34] F. Duarte and A. Fitzgerald, "Guiding principles for a reflexive approach to teaching organisation studies," in *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice (JUTLP)*, vol. 3, no. 1, article 3, 2006, pp. 15-23. <http://ro.uow.edu.au/jutlp/vol3/iss1/3>
- [35] <https://youtu.be/vbYH8yaIVQw>, Reflexivity: Reflective vs Reflexive; Reflection vs Reflexion, Jul 29, 2017
- [36] <https://youtu.be/4YGSTvH6vQQ>, Reflective and Reflexive Practice, Dec 5, 2015.
- [37] M. Seitova, "Student teachers' perceptions of reflective practice," in *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, vol. 6, no. 4, 2019, pp. 765-772. <http://iojet.org/index.php/IOJET/article/view/723>
- [38] K. Vangrieken, F. Dochy, E. Raes and E. Kyndt, "Teacher collaboration: A systematic review," in *Educational Research Review*, vol. 15, 2015, pp. 17-40. DOI: 10.1016/j.edurev.2015.04.002
- [39] R. Woodland, M. K. Lee and J. Randall, "A validation study of the teacher collaboration assessment survey," in *Journal Educational Research and Evaluatann An International Journal on Theory and Practice*, vol.19, no, 5, 2013, pp. 442-460. Published online: 18 Jun 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2013.795118>

- [40] S. Liu and H. C. Tsai, "Teachers' experiences of collaborating in school teaching teams," in *Asian Social Science*, vol. 13, no. 2, Canadian Center of Science and Education, 2017, pp. 159-168. DOI: 10.5539/ass.v13n2p159. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ass.v13n2p159>
- [41] S. J. Damore and C. Murray, "Urban elementary school teachers' perspectives regarding collaborative teaching practices," in *Remedial and Special Education Hammill Institute on Disabilities*, vol. , no , SAGE, 2008, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0741932508321007>
- [42] J. Killion, "High-quality collaboration benefits teachers and students," in *Lessons from Research, JSD*, vol. 36, no. 5, 2015.
- [43] A. Akyel, "Collaboration to explore teaching: A case study report," in *TESL Canada Journal*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2000. Uploaded by Ayse Akyel on 19 October 2015. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228349422>
- [44] M. Enisa, "The effect of collaborative reflection on EFL teaching," in *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 2, Elsevier, Science Direct online, 2010, pp. 3888-3891.
- [45] G. V. Lee and B.G. Barnett, "Using reflective questioning to promote collaborative dialogue," in *Journal of Staff Development*, vol. 15, no. 1, 1994, pp.16- 20.
- [46] J. M. G. Martinez, "How effective is collaborative reflective practice in enabling cognitive transformation in English language teachers?", in *Reflective Practice*, vol. 19, no. 4, 2018, pp. 427-446, DOI: 10.1080/14623943.2018.1479688
- [47] H. Tasdemir and T. Yildirim, "Collaborative teaching from English language instructors' perspectives," in *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, vol. 13, no. 2, 2017, pp. 632-642. <http://www.jlls.org>
- [48] S. M. Pratt, S. M. Imbody, L. D. Wolf, and A. L. Patterson, "Co-planning in Co-teaching: A Practical Solution," in *Intervention in School and Clinic*, vol. 52, no. 4, Hammill Institute on Disabilities: SAGE, 2017, pp. 243-249.
- [49] E. Fennick and D. Liddy, "Responsibilities and preparation for collaborative teaching: co-teachers'," in *Teacher Education and Special Education*, vol. 24 , no.3, 2001, pp. 229-240.
- [50] V. L. Austin, "Teachers' beliefs about co-teaching," in *Remedial and Special Education*, vol. 22, no 4, Jul-Aug 2001, pp 245-255. URL: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/074193250102200408>
- [51] M. W. Kamens, J. P. Susko1, and J. S. Elliott, "Evaluation and supervision of co-teaching: A study of administrator practices in New Jersey," in *NASSP Bulletin*, vol. 97, no. 2, SAGE Publications Reprints and permissions, 2013, pp 166-190 sagepub.com/journalsPermissions.nav DOI: 10.1177/0192636513476337 bul.sagepub.com
- [52] P. Tremblay, "Comparative outcomes of two instructional models for students with learning disabilities: inclusion with co-teaching and solo-taught special education," in *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, vol. 13, no. 4, MA: John Wiley & Sons Ltd, 2013, pp. 251-258. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1471-3802.2012.01270.x>
- [53] J. Park, "English co-teaching and teacher collaboration: A micro-interactional perspective," in *System*, vol. 44, Elsevier, June 2014, pp. 34-44,. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0346251X14000256>
- [54] W. Luo, "Chapter thirteen collaborative teaching of EFL by native and non-native English speaking teachers in Taiwan," in *The NNEST Lens: Non Native English Speakers in TESOL*, A. Mahboob Ed. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2010 <http://nnestevo2014.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/69375483/MahboobChapter%2013.pdf>
- [55] V. F. Burns and S. Mintzberg, "Co-teaching as teacher training: experiential accounts of two doctoral students," in *College Teaching*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 94-99, 2019, DOI: 10.1080/87567555.2018.1558169
- [56] M. Sotiriou, "Investigating student perceptions of student-staff partnership," in *Shaping Higher Education with Students Ways to Connect Research and Teaching*. Vincent C. H. Tong, Alex Standen, Mina Sotiriou, Eds, UCL Press, 2018, ch. 1.4. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt21c4tcm.10>
- [57] Faculty of Arts and Humanities, BUE, 2019 website <https://www.bue.edu/ faculties-departments/arts-and-humanities/about-arts-and-humanities/#PageTitle>
- [58] S. Flakes, "Inclusion Corner: The art of co-teaching," in *Multibriefs: Exclusive*, December, 2014, <http://exclusive.multibriefs.com/content/inclusion-corner-zthe-art-of-co-teaching/education>
- [59] N. Rashidi and Z. Javidanmehr, "Pondering on issues and obstacles in reflective teaching in Iranian context," in *American Journal of Linguistics*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2012, pp. 19-27. DOI: 10.5923/j.linguistics.20120103.01
- [60] H. S. Afshar and M. Farahani, "Inhibitors to EFL teachers' reflective teaching and EFL learners' reflective thinking and the role of teaching experience and academic degree in reflection perception," in *Reflective Practice International and Multidisciplinary Perspectives*, vol 19, no 1, Taylor & Francis online, 2018, pp. 46- 67. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14623943.2017.1351353>
- [61] R. A. Villa, *Co-Teaching, A guide to co-teaching - Practical tips for facilitating student learning: A multimedia kit for professional development*, Thousand Oaks 2nd ed., 2017. <https://www.ravillabayridge.com/Co-Teaching-Full-Day-20171024>
- [62] S. Y. Al-Shareef and R. A. Al-Qarni, "The effectiveness of using teacher-teacher wikis in collaborative lesson planning and its impact on teacher's classroom performance," in *English Language Teaching*, vol. 9, no. 4, Canadian Center of Science and Education, 2016, pp. 186-202, doi: 10.5539/elt.v9n4p186 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n4p186>
- [63] J. Tice, "Reflective teaching: Exploring our own classroom practice," in *Teaching English*, British Council, BBC 2004. <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/reflective-teaching-exploring-our-own-classroom-practice>
- [64] T. Heick, "10 ways to be a more reflective teacher," in *Teachthought we grow teachers*, November 2019. <https://www.teachthought.com/pedagogy/reflective-teacher-reflective-teaching/>
- [65] P. Hall and A. Simeral, "Stop, practice, collaborate: The cycle of reflective teaching," in *Teachthought we grow teachers*, April 2019. <https://www.teachthought.com/pedagogy/the-cycle-of-reflective-teaching/>
- [66] V. Himmelsbach, "Reflective teaching: Some tips to get started" November, 2018. <https://tophat.com/blog/reflective-teaching-get-started>
- [67] "A practical guide to enabling effective teacher reflection 2019 V3.pdf," "Your practical guide to: Enabling effective teacher reflection," in *IRIS connect*, UK:2019. Posted by Alexandra Spalding on 13 May, 2019. <https://cdn2.hubspot.net/hubfs/1603217/A%20practical%20guide%20to%20enabling%20effective%20teacher%20reflection%202019%20V3.pdf>
- [68] <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-reflective-teaching-definition-methods-quiz.html>
- [69] <https://www.slideshare.net/NathanHutchings/being-a-reflexive-teacher>
- [70] M. R. Morris, "A survey of collaborative web search practices," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ACM New York, NY, USA, 2008, pp. 1657-1660.
- [71] P. Konieczny, "Wikis and Wikipedia as a teaching tool," in *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, vol. 4, no.1, 2007, pp. 15-34. <http://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan.PDF>
- [72] H. Kioumarsi, H. B. Shalmani and M. H. Meymeh, "Wikis and wiki-based activities: On peer collaboration in wikispaces and Its implications for the development of the L2 writing ability," in *CALL-EJ*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2018, pp. 139-165. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/291c/4a7262237d031809bf6de38623e0a25db422.pdf?ga=2.36768035.2005531845.1576010049-642765562.1576010049>
- [73] J. C. Richards, "Towards reflective teaching," in *The Teacher Trainer- A Practical Journal for those who Train, Mentor, and Educate TESOL Teachers*, archive, back articles online 2019. <https://www.tttjournal.co.uk/back-articles/>
- [74] J. C. Richards and C. Lockhart, *Reflective teaching in second language classrooms*, Cambridge Language Education, Cambridge University Press, 2007.
- [75] A.Q. Pacheco, "Reflective teaching and its impact on foreign language teaching," in *Revista Electrónica "Actualidades Investigativas en Educación"*, vol. 5, Número Extraordinario, 2005.Uploaded by Allen Quesada on 23 May 2014.
- [76] "Three benefits of reflective teaching and how to practice it in your classroom," March 2019, Online and On-site Graduate Courses for Educators. <https://plsclasses.com/>, <https://plsclasses.com/tag/reflective-teaching/>, <https://plsclasses.com/three-benefits-of-reflective-teaching-PLS-Classes>,
- [77] A. Spalding, "5 benefits of being a reflective teacher," in "Practical Guide to Enabling Effective Teacher Reflection," *IRIS* posted on 13 May, 2019. <https://blog.irisconnect.com/uk/blog/5-benefits-of-encouraging-teacher-self-reflection>
- [78] L. Dabbs, "The Value in Reflection for a New Teacher | Main | Finding Your Teacher Voice, 3 Tips to Support a Reflective Teaching Practice," in *Education Week Teacher*, February, 2018. https://blogs.edweek.org/teachers/new_teacher_chat/2018/02/3_tips_to_support_a_reflective_teaching_practice.html

- [79] P. Graham, "Improving teacher effectiveness through structured collaboration: A case study of a professional learning community," in *Research in Middle Level Education (RMLE) online*, vol. 31, no. 1, 2007. Published online: 25 Aug 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19404476.2007.11462044>.